

The Criteria for Using Mursal Hadiths as Evidence According to Imam Al-Shafi'i: A Study in the Principles of Hadith Methodology

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Abstract

Objectives: This study aims to identify the criteria governing the use of mursal hadith as evidence according to Imam Al-Shafi'i, to explore the scholarly foundations underlying his acceptance or rejection of such reports, and to highlight his critical methodology in balancing hadith transmission standards with principles of legal reasoning.

Methodology: The study employs an inductive and analytical approach by examining Al-Shafi'i's statements concerning mursal hadith in his works, tracing his practical applications, and analyzing them to derive the principles governing his position on the evidential value of mursal reports.

Results: The study concludes that Imam Al-Shafi'i neither accepted nor rejected mursal hadith categorically. Rather, he considered it admissible under specific conditions, including that the transmitter be a trustworthy senior Tābi'i and that the report be supported by corroborating evidence or reliable indications that strengthen its authenticity. The findings further reveal that his approach combines rigorous hadith criticism with the requirements of juristic reasoning.

Conclusion: The study concludes that Imam Al-Shafi'i's position on mursal hadith represents a balanced methodological model that integrates critical scrutiny with juristic flexibility. His acceptance of mursal reports is based on precise scholarly criteria that safeguard the authority of the Sunnah and regulate legal inference.

Keywords: Mursal Hadith, Imam Al-Shafi'i, Hadith Authentication, Acceptance Criteria, Hadith Criticism, Usul al-Fiqh

Introduction

Praise be to Allah, Lord of the worlds. The ultimate success belongs to the righteous. May peace and blessings be upon the Seal of the Prophets and Messengers, and upon his pure family and noble companions.

The mursal hadith occupies a significant position among the disciplines of Hadith studies and represents one of the most intricate issues affecting legal reasoning and juristic inference. The acceptance or rejection of this category of hadith has far-reaching scholarly and legal implications. Consequently, it has received considerable attention from leading hadith critics and jurists, foremost among them Imam al-Shafi'i, who developed a coherent critical methodology for evaluating transmitted reports while preserving both the integrity of the Prophetic tradition and the principles governing its use as legal evidence.

Imam al-Shafi'i's approach to mursal hadith stands as a distinctive model of methodological balance. He neither rejected mursal reports categorically nor accepted them unconditionally. Rather, he established a set of precise criteria and rigorous conditions governing their admissibility as evidence, thereby ensuring the soundness of legal argumentation and safeguarding Islamic law from methodological inconsistency.

This study seeks to clarify the concept of mursal hadith and to examine Imam al-Shafi'i's position regarding its evidentiary value. It further aims to identify and analyze the criteria he established for accepting mursal reports through an inductive and analytical examination of his statements and practical applications. In doing so, the study highlights the scholarly and juristic significance of his methodology and contributes to a deeper understanding of legal reasoning within the Shafi'i tradition, while promoting greater methodological awareness in both Hadith and legal studies.

Research Problem

The research problem arises from the diversity of scholarly perceptions regarding Imam al-Shafi'i's position on mursal hadith and the resulting confusion between mursal reports that are categorically rejected and those accepted under specific conditions. Moreover, the criteria governing their acceptance are dispersed throughout his writings and statements and have not been systematically compiled in a manner that reveals their underlying hadith and legal-theoretical foundations.

Accordingly, this study seeks to answer the following central question:

What are the criteria established by Imam al-Shafi'i for accepting mursal hadith as evidence, and what are their hadith and legal-theoretical foundations?

Research Objectives

This study aims to:

1. Examine and establish Imam al-Shafi'i's position on mursal hadith through his explicit statements and practical applications.
2. Identify and analyze the criteria governing the acceptance of mursal reports according to Imam al-Shafi'i from both hadith and legal-theoretical perspectives.
3. Highlight the impact of these criteria on legal reasoning and juristic *ijtihad* within the Shafi'i methodology.

Research Methodology

The study adopts an inductive approach by tracing Imam al-Shafi'i's discussions of mursal hadith in their original sources. It also employs an analytical approach to examine these texts and derive the principles governing the acceptance and use of mursal reports. In addition, a limited comparative approach is utilized where necessary to demonstrate the distinctive features of al-Shafi'i's methodology in comparison with other hadith and juristic approaches.

Previous Studies

A considerable number of studies in the fields of Hadith sciences and Islamic legal theory have addressed the issue of mursal hadith in terms of its definition, evidentiary value, and the various scholarly positions concerning its acceptance. Some works have also examined the methodologies adopted by leading scholars, including Imam al-Shafi'i, in dealing with mursal reports.

However, most of these studies have treated the subject within broader discussions of Hadith methodology or disputed evidences in legal theory, without dedicating specific attention to the criteria established by Imam al-Shafi'i for the acceptance of mursal reports. Furthermore, these criteria have rarely been analyzed through an integrated framework combining both Hadith criticism and legal theory.

While some studies have discussed al-Shafi'i's position based primarily on his treatment of the issue in *Al-Risalah* and have outlined the conditions he set for accepting mursal reports, such discussions are generally brief or presented within broad comparative analyses of legal schools. Consequently, they often lack a comprehensive examination of his texts and a detailed analysis of how these criteria were applied throughout his legal and hadith writings.

The significance of the present study therefore lies in its attempt to collect and analyze the criteria governing the acceptance of mursal hadith according to Imam al-Shafi'i directly from

their primary sources. It further seeks to examine these criteria within the broader framework of his hadith and legal-theoretical methodology, highlighting the complementarity between the two disciplines in addressing this issue.

Structure of the Study

The study consists of an introduction, two main sections, and a conclusion, arranged as follows: Introduction: Includes the significance of the study, the research problem, objectives, methodology, previous studies, and the overall research plan.

Section One: Mursal Hadith and Imam al-Shafi'i's Position Regarding It.

Section Two: The Criteria for the Acceptance of Mursal Hadith as Evidence According to Imam al-Shafi'i.

Conclusion: Presents the main findings and recommendations of the study.

Section One: Mursal Hadith and Imam al-Shafi'i's Position Toward It The First Requirement: The Concept of Mursal Hadith

Defining the concept of mursal hadith constitutes one of the central issues in Hadith studies, as differences in its definition directly affect the evaluation of reports and their admissibility as legal evidence. Due to the problem of discontinuity in transmission and the anonymity of the omitted narrator, hadith scholars devoted considerable attention to this category of reports. They clarified its linguistic and technical meanings and distinguished it from other forms of interrupted transmission, thereby establishing the basis for critical judgments concerning its authenticity and evidentiary value (Al-'Alā'ī, 1986; Ibn Ḥajar, 1984; Abū Shahbah, n.d.).

Linguistic Meaning of Mursal

Linguistically, the term *irsāl* denotes releasing, letting go, or sending forth without restriction. It is derived from the verb *arsala*, meaning "to release" or "to let something proceed without restraint." This meaning appears in the Qur'anic verse: "Do you not see that We have sent the devils upon the disbelievers, inciting them ever onward?" (Qur'an 19:83).

In the context of hadith transmission, the term came to signify the omission of part of the chain of transmission (*isnād*), whereby the report is conveyed without complete linkage to all transmitters. In this sense, the narrator is regarded as having "released" the report without connecting it through the full chain of authorities. Consequently, the term implies a degree of incompleteness from the perspective of hadith methodology. Al-'Alā'ī (1986, p. 23) explained this by stating that the transmitter effectively "releases the chain of transmission without identifying the omitted narrator."

Technical Definition of Mursal Hadith

The majority of hadith scholars define mursal hadith as a report transmitted by a Successor (*tābi'ī*) directly from the Prophet ﷺ without mentioning the Companion intermediary. This definition was adopted by al-Khaṭīb al-Baghdādī (1357 AH) in *Al-Kifāyah fī 'Ilm al-Riwāyah* and later affirmed by Ibn al-Ṣalāḥ (1986), who considered this understanding the prevailing definition among hadith specialists.

Similarly, Imam al-Shafi'i explicitly referred to reports transmitted by individuals below the rank of the senior Successors as mursal, stating that anyone possessing adequate knowledge and critical awareness would be cautious regarding the mursal reports transmitted by those who were not among the leading Successors (Al-Shafi'i, 1938, p. 467).

Ibn al-Ṣalāḥ (1986) further classified mursal reports among the categories of weak hadith due to the interruption in their chains of transmission, although he acknowledged that supporting evidence might strengthen such reports and elevate their status. Al-Nawawī (1985) likewise emphasized that the omission of a Companion does not entirely remove concerns regarding the identity and reliability of the omitted transmitter, despite the universally accepted integrity of the Companions.

Mursal Hadith and Its Distinction from Other Forms of Interrupted Transmission

Hadith scholars carefully distinguished mursal reports from other categories of interrupted transmission. In a mursal report, the omission specifically concerns the Companion between the Successor and the Prophet ﷺ. This differs from a munqaṭi' report, in which the interruption occurs at an unspecified point within the chain; from a muḍal report, in which two or more consecutive narrators are omitted; and from a mu'allaq report, in which one or more transmitters are omitted from the beginning of the chain.

Al-Khaṭīb al-Baghḍādī (1357 AH) discussed these distinctions in *Al-Kifāyah*, while Ibn Ḥajar (2000) elaborated upon them in *Nuzhat al-Nazar*, emphasizing that different forms of interruption necessitate different critical evaluations and legal judgments regarding acceptance and rejection.

Furthermore, mursal transmission differs from *tadlīs* (concealment in transmission). While *tadlīs* involves creating the impression of uninterrupted transmission despite uncertainty regarding direct hearing, *irsāl* explicitly acknowledges the omission of an intermediary narrator.

This distinction is essential for understanding the varying methodologies adopted by Muslim scholars in evaluating mursal reports, particularly that of Imam al-Shafi'i, whose position was founded upon a precise understanding of the nature and implications of such discontinuity. His methodology will be examined in detail in the following section.

The Second Requirement: Imam al-Shafi'i's Position on Mursal Hadith

Mursal hadith occupied a central position within Imam al-Shafi'i's critical methodology, as it represented one of the principal criteria by which reports were evaluated for their admissibility as legal evidence. In several of his works, most notably *Al-Risālah*, al-Shafi'i emphasized that the fundamental requirement for the acceptance of a report is the continuity of its chain of transmission (*ittiṣāl al-isnād*). A connected chain ensures the preservation of accurate transmission and protects the Prophetic Sunnah from error and unauthorized additions. Consequently, because a mursal report contains a break in its chain, it cannot, in principle, serve as independent legal proof (Al-Shafi'i, 1938, pp. 464–465; Ibn 'Abd al-Barr, 2017, Vol. 1, p. 195).

Despite this general principle, al-Shafi'i's position was not one of absolute rejection. Rather, it reflected a balanced and nuanced approach that distinguished between a solitary mursal report lacking supporting evidence and one reinforced by credible corroborative indicators. He maintained that when a mursal report originates from a trustworthy and meticulous Successor and is supported by a *musnad* (fully connected) narration, the opinion of the majority of scholars, or corroborating reports from the Companions, it may be accepted—not on the basis of its independent authority, but because of the supporting evidence accompanying it (Al-Shafi'i, 1938, p. 462).

This position reveals the sophistication of al-Shafi'i's methodology in dealing with transmitted reports. He sought to preserve the integrity of the Sunnah by avoiding reliance on inadequately verified narrations, while simultaneously recognizing the evidentiary value of mursal reports when strong indicators supported their authenticity. In doing so, he established a moderate and methodologically coherent framework that significantly influenced later developments in hadith criticism and legal theory.

The General Principle Governing Imam al-Shafi'i's Position on Mursal Hadith

Al-Shafi'i maintained that reports used as legal evidence must, as a rule, possess an uninterrupted chain of transmission. The requirement of continuity safeguards the reliability of transmission and protects the Sunnah from mistakes and distortions. Based on this principle, a

mursal report does not attain the status of independently admissible evidence because of the interruption inherent in its chain.

Al-Shafi'i explicitly articulated this position in *Al-Risālah*, arguing that the omission of the intermediary between the Successor and the Prophet ﷺ creates uncertainty regarding the identity and reliability of the omitted narrator. Since the omitted transmitter may be either trustworthy or otherwise, reliance upon such a report cannot be justified at the outset. This demonstrates that al-Shafi'i's reservation concerning mursal reports stemmed from methodological caution rather than a blanket distrust of the Successors or a wholesale rejection of their narrations.

In outlining his criteria, he stated that the reliability of a transmitter should be assessed by examining those whom he names in his narrations. If he consistently transmits from known and reliable authorities, this strengthens confidence in the reports that he narrates without naming his sources (Al-Shafi'i, 1938, p. 463).

Al-Shafi'i's Evidences for Rejecting Mursal Hadith as Independent Proof

Al-Shafi'i based his reluctance to accept mursal reports as independent evidence on several methodological considerations.

1. The Unknown Status of the Omitted Narrator

A Successor may narrate from trustworthy authorities, but he may also narrate from individuals whose reliability is questionable. Once the intermediary narrator is omitted, there is no means of verifying his status. This uncertainty undermines the evidentiary value of the report. Al-Shafi'i therefore argued that a mursal report cannot possess the same evidentiary force as a connected narration because the omitted narrator may be someone whose testimony would not be accepted if identified (Al-Shafi'i, 1938, p. 464).

2. The Possibility of Error or Misremembering

Al-Shafi'i also recognized that omission within a chain may result from forgetfulness, abbreviation, or inaccuracies in transmission. Such possibilities conflict with the requirement of precision (*ḍabt*) that he considered essential for reports used as legal evidence.

Accordingly, he observed that even when multiple mursal reports support one another, it remains possible that they originate from a single weak source whose identity remains unknown. Likewise, the agreement of a Companion's personal opinion with the content of a mursal report may strengthen its credibility but does not eliminate the possibility of error in transmission (Al-Shafi'i, 1938, pp. 464–465).

3. Departure from the General Principle Governing Accepted Reports

According to al-Shafi'i, legal authority is fundamentally established through authentic reports with uninterrupted chains. Any report departing from this standard requires additional evidence to restore its credibility.

For this reason, he maintained that a mursal report cannot be accepted unless supported by independent corroborating evidence. He further argued that the mursal reports transmitted by later Successors are generally less reliable than those transmitted by the senior Successors because later transmitters often narrated from a wider range of authorities, some of whom were weak or unknown. Moreover, the greater chronological distance from the Companions increased the likelihood of transmission errors and uncertainties regarding intermediaries (Al-Shafi'i, 1938, pp. 465–467).

Al-Shafi'i therefore concluded that anyone possessing sound scholarly judgment would naturally exercise caution toward the mursal reports of transmitters below the rank of the senior Successors (Al-Shafi'i, 1938, p. 467).

This reasoning was later summarized by Ibn 'Abd al-Barr, who explained that scholars rejected mursal reports because the reliability of every transmitter in the chain must be established.

Since many Successors narrated from both reliable and unreliable authorities, ignorance regarding the omitted intermediary prevents verification of the report's authenticity. Consequently, the report loses its evidentiary force due to uncertainty concerning the missing narrator (Ibn 'Abd al-Barr, 2017, Vol. 1, p. 197).

A Brief Comparison Between Imam al-Shafi'i's Methodology and That of Other Scholars
Scholars differed considerably in their treatment of mursal reports due to variations in their approaches to hadith criticism and legal reasoning. Al-Shafi'i's methodology was distinguished by its combination of caution in accepting reports and willingness to consider corroborated mursal narrations. While he regarded continuity of transmission as the norm, he accepted mursal reports only when supported by evidence capable of mitigating concerns regarding interruption and possible error.

In contrast, Imam Abu Hanifah and many scholars of the Hanafi school adopted a broader approach toward the acceptance of mursal reports, particularly when transmitted by trustworthy Successors known for their legal expertise and reliability. They maintained that the integrity of such transmitters and their discernment regarding their sources justified acting upon these reports. Al-Jaṣṣāṣ (1994, Vol. 3, p. 147) explicitly stated that the accepted position among Hanafi scholars was the admissibility of the mursal reports of both the Successors and their successors unless evidence suggested unreliability. Al-Sarakhsī (1431 AH, Vol. 1, p. 363) likewise affirmed that mursal reports transmitted during the second and third generations of Islam constitute valid legal evidence according to Hanafi scholars.

A similar tendency appears in the Maliki tradition. Imam Malik accepted the mursal reports of senior Successors, particularly when they corresponded to the established practice of the people of Madinah. Such communal practice served, in his view, as a strong indicator of the authenticity of the report. As Ibn 'Abd al-Barr (2017, Vol. 1, p. 193) explained, Malik generally considered both musnad and mursal reports authoritative unless contradicted by the established practice of Madinah.

Imam Ahmad ibn Hanbal adopted a more intermediate position. Although he preferred connected reports whenever available, he was willing to rely upon mursal reports in the absence of stronger evidence and often preferred weak hadith over purely rational opinion. Nevertheless, his acceptance of mursal reports was not unconditional; it depended upon the absence of conflicting evidence and the soundness of the report's meaning. Al-Athram reported that Ahmad would occasionally act upon a mursal narration when no stronger opposing evidence existed (Al-Khaṭīb al-Baghdādī, 1421 AH, Vol. 1, p. 543).

This comparison demonstrates the distinctive nature of al-Shafi'i's methodology. Unlike approaches that based acceptance primarily on the status of the transmitter or on prevailing legal practice, al-Shafi'i required the convergence of multiple corroborative factors before accepting a mursal report. His approach was therefore more rigorous and more closely aligned with the principles of hadith criticism, while remaining firmly connected to juristic reasoning and legal methodology.

Section Two: The Criteria Governing the Acceptance of Mursal Hadith According to Imam al-Shafi‘i

This section constitutes the core of the present study. It demonstrates how Imam al-Shafi‘i moved beyond merely expressing a theoretical position on mursal hadith to establishing a precise methodological framework regulating its acceptance and determining the circumstances under which it may serve as legal evidence. These criteria reveal an integrated critical approach that seeks, on the one hand, to preserve the integrity of the Prophetic Sunnah from unreliable transmissions and, on the other, to avoid dismissing reports whose authenticity is supported by credible evidence and corroborating indications.

The First Requirement: Criteria Related to the Transmitting Narrator (al-Mursil)

Imam al-Shafi‘i attached particular importance to the status of the narrator who transmits a mursal report. Since mursal transmission necessarily involves the omission of a narrator from the chain, evaluating the reliability and scholarly standing of the transmitter becomes one of the most important means of assessing the report itself.

1. The Requirement that the Transmitter Be Among the Senior Successors

Al-Shafi‘i stipulated that the transmitter of a mursal report should belong to the senior generation of the Successors (*kibār al-tābi‘īn*) who were known to have direct contact with the Companions. In his view, proximity to the Companions reduces the likelihood of transmission through unreliable intermediaries and strengthens confidence in the source of the report.

Consequently, not all mursal reports occupy the same evidentiary status. Their acceptability varies according to the scholarly rank, reliability, and generation of the transmitter. Al-Shafi‘i explained that when a senior Successor narrates a disconnected report from the Prophet ﷺ, that report should be subjected to further examination through a set of established criteria (Al-Shafi‘i, 1938, p. 461).

He further clarified that a distinction must be drawn between the early Successors who extensively interacted with the Companions and later transmitters whose contact with them was more limited. According to al-Shafi‘i, the likelihood of unreliable intermediaries increases as one moves further away from the generation of the Companions (Al-Shafi‘i, 1938, p. 467).

Al-Shafi‘i explicitly rejected the unrestricted acceptance of the mursal reports transmitted by later Successors, arguing that they often narrated from a wider range of authorities, that weaknesses in the origins of some of their reports could frequently be detected, and that the greater number of intermediary links increased the possibility of error and uncertainty regarding the reliability of omitted transmitters (Al-Shafi‘i, 1938, pp. 465–466).

This reflects a critical hadith-based methodology grounded in practical examination of chains of transmission rather than merely theoretical assumptions. Since later Successors had less extensive contact with the Companions, they were more likely to transmit through intermediaries whose reliability could not always be verified.

2. The Requirement of Reliability and Precision in Transmission

Al-Shafi‘i did not consider belonging to the senior generation of Successors sufficient in itself. He additionally required that the transmitter be known for accuracy, careful verification, and consistent transmission from trustworthy authorities.

This condition demonstrates his insistence upon combining personal integrity (*‘adālah*) with precision in transmission (*ḍabt*), rather than relying solely on favorable assumptions regarding a narrator’s character. In this respect, his methodology closely resembles that of the leading hadith critics.

Al-Shafi‘i explained that the reliability of a transmitter may be assessed by examining the authorities from whom he openly narrates. If he consistently names reliable and well-known transmitters and demonstrates agreement with other trustworthy hadith scholars when narrating

shared reports, this serves as evidence supporting the reliability of his mursal narrations. Conversely, if he frequently disagrees with reliable transmitters or narrates from unknown or unreliable authorities, confidence in his mursal reports is significantly weakened (Al-Shafi'i, 1938, p. 463).

The Second Requirement: Criteria Related to the Mursal Report Itself

Al-Shafi'i's methodology was not limited to evaluating the transmitter. He also subjected the content of the report itself to critical examination and assessed its consistency with established legal and textual principles.

1. Agreement with an Authentic Connected Report or Established Tradition

If a mursal report corresponds to an authentic or acceptable connected narration (musnad), the mursal report functions as supporting evidence rather than an independent source of proof. In such cases, it indicates the circulation and recognition of the reported meaning among scholars and transmitters.

This demonstrates that, in al-Shafi'i's methodology, legal authority ultimately rests upon the connected report, while the mursal narration serves only as corroborative evidence. He explicitly stated that when trustworthy scholars transmit the same report through a connected chain with substantially identical wording or meaning, this strengthens confidence in both the omitted source and the reliability of the mursal transmitter (Al-Shafi'i, 1938, p. 464).

2. Agreement with the Opinion of the Majority of Scholars

Al-Shafi'i also regarded conformity between a mursal report and the opinions of the majority of scholars as a significant corroborative indicator. Such agreement suggests that the report possesses an established basis within scholarly tradition, even if no complete chain of transmission has survived.

This position reflects his appreciation of scholarly consensus and widespread juristic agreement as supporting evidence. Al-Shafi'i maintained that if no supporting musnad report exists, one should examine whether the content of the mursal narration corresponds to statements transmitted from the Companions or to the established views of leading scholars. Such agreement indicates that the transmitter likely relied upon an authentic source (Al-Shafi'i, 1938, pp. 462–463).

The Third Requirement: Criteria Related to Corroborating Evidence

A central feature of al-Shafi'i's methodology is that acceptance of a mursal report depends upon corroborative evidence rather than upon the mursal transmission itself. Supporting indications therefore form an indispensable element of the evaluative process.

1. Transmission Through Another Independent Mursal Chain

If the same report is transmitted through more than one independent mursal chain, this increases confidence that the report possesses a genuine historical basis and that the omission is not the result of an isolated error by a single transmitter.

Al-Shafi'i argued that when a mursal narration is supported by another independent mursal report transmitted through different authorities, such corroboration strengthens its credibility, although this form of support remains weaker than corroboration through a connected chain of transmission (Al-Shafi'i, 1938, p. 462).

2. Conformity with the Practice of the Companions or Successor Jurists

Among the strongest forms of corroboration recognized by al-Shafi'i is evidence that the Companions or leading jurists among the Successors acted in accordance with the content of the mursal report. Such practice suggests that the underlying meaning of the report was recognized and accepted, even if the complete chain of transmission was not preserved.

Al-Shafi'i observed that when the opinion of a Companion coincides with the content of a mursal report, this constitutes a powerful indication of the report's authenticity. The same

reasoning applies when prominent jurists endorse and apply the substance of the report in their legal rulings (Al-Shafi'i, 1938, pp. 464–465).

Practical Applications of Imam al-Shafi'i's Methodology

The practical implementation of al-Shafi'i's approach to mursal hadith is evident throughout his legal and methodological writings. He never accepted mursal reports unconditionally; rather, he consistently applied the criteria outlined above before relying upon them as evidence. One of the most prominent examples is his treatment of the mursal narrations of Sa'īd ibn al-Musayyib. Al-Shafi'i regarded these reports as among the most reliable examples of mursal transmission because of Ibn al-Musayyib's exceptional reputation for accuracy, careful transmission, and extensive contact with the Companions.

Al-Shafi'i stated that he knew of no mursal narration transmitted by Sa'īd ibn al-Musayyib for which corroborating evidence could not be found. Furthermore, he observed that Ibn al-Musayyib consistently transmitted from trustworthy authorities, unlike some transmitters who narrated from unknown or unreliable individuals and transmitted reports lacking any supporting evidence. Consequently, al-Shafi'i accepted the mursal reports of transmitters possessing qualifications similar to those of Ibn al-Musayyib while rejecting reports transmitted under less reliable circumstances (Al-Shafi'i, 1983, Vol. 3, p. 192).

A notable example appears in the legal issue of adjudication based on a single witness accompanied by an oath. Al-Shafi'i cited a mursal report transmitted by Sa'īd ibn al-Musayyib stating that the Prophet ﷺ ruled on the basis of one witness together with the claimant's oath. He accepted this report because it was reinforced by connected narrations and by reports indicating that certain Companions acted in accordance with its content. Thus, the report became admissible not because of its mursal status, but because of the corroborating evidence supporting it (Al-Shafi'i, 1983, Vol. 6, p. 274).

More generally, al-Shafi'i consistently maintained that a mursal report transmitted by a trustworthy authority gains evidentiary strength when supported by another narration, a statement from a Companion, or established scholarly practice. Such corroboration demonstrates that the report possesses an authentic foundation and therefore deserves consideration within legal reasoning.

This methodology is elaborated in detail in *Al-Risālah*, where al-Shafi'i outlines the conditions governing the acceptance of mursal reports and the various forms of evidence capable of strengthening them. It is likewise reflected in *Al-Umm*, where he occasionally relied upon mursal reports after demonstrating their support through corroborating traditions and legal precedents. These applications vividly illustrate his careful balance between safeguarding the integrity of the Sunnah and avoiding the rejection of reports supported by credible evidence.

Conclusion

This study has examined Imam al-Shafi'i's methodology regarding the acceptance of mursal hadith and the criteria he established for its evidentiary use. The findings of the study may be summarized as follows:

1. Imam al-Shafi'i's position on mursal hadith was not a marginal opinion or an isolated juristic preference; rather, it emerged from a comprehensive critical methodology aimed at preserving the integrity of the Prophetic Sunnah and regulating the principles governing its use as legal evidence according to well-defined scholarly standards.
2. Al-Shafi'i maintained that the fundamental basis for legal proof lies in authentic reports transmitted through uninterrupted chains of narration. Accordingly, he regarded discontinuity in transmission as a deficiency that, in principle, weakens a report's evidentiary value. Nevertheless, this did not lead him to reject mursal reports categorically.
3. Imam al-Shafi'i developed a precise and coherent framework governing the acceptance of mursal hadith. This framework encompassed an assessment of the transmitter's reliability, an examination of the content of the report, and consideration of corroborating indicators capable

of strengthening its credibility. These criteria were not merely theoretical constructs but were consistently reflected in his legal and methodological writings. His approach therefore represents a balanced synthesis between the rigorous standards of hadith critics in evaluating chains of transmission and the insight of jurists in understanding meanings and weighing legal evidence.

4. Al-Shafi'i's methodology played a significant role in regulating juristic disagreement by preventing the unrestricted acceptance of mursal reports while simultaneously avoiding the dismissal of reports supported by credible evidence. In this way, he made a substantial contribution to the development of principles governing the use of the Sunnah as legal proof and established a lasting methodological connection between Hadith studies and Islamic legal theory.

In light of these findings, the study recommends further specialized research into the methodologies employed by the leading hadith critics and jurists in evaluating disputed categories of reports. It also highlights the value of drawing upon al-Shafi'i's methodological approach in contemporary Hadith scholarship as a means of strengthening critical awareness, enhancing the soundness of legal reasoning, and contributing to the ongoing development of research in the fields of Sunnah studies and Islamic legal theory.

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